

**TRusted, Citizen - LEA collAboratiOn
over sOcial Networks**

**Learn
about
TRILLION**

**Work
together**

Working together on a safe society

Community policing promotes the implementation of bi-directional collaboration channels between citizens and Law Enforcement Agencies (LEAs). By enhancing the discovery of relevant and up to date information, it speeds up the detection of risks, eases their prevention and builds a continuum of collaboration which motivates citizens and LEAs to work together for a safer society. In September 2018, the TRILLION project will deliver a fully-fledged platform and mobile applications to support the extensive collaboration between citizens and LEAs for incident discovery, prediction, reporting and interaction whilst ensuring that privacy and data protection are taken into account.

Using the TRILLION platform, *citizens* will support the achievement of a better urban security management by

- *reporting crimes, suspicious behaviour and incidents*
- *identifying hazards*
- *assisting LEAs through active participation.*

At the same time, *LEAs* will be able to

- *detect incidents in a more efficient, content and context aware manner*
- *locate on-site citizens, other LEA representatives and first responders and communicate with them*
- *request more information and assign specific actions to address on-going incidents.*

TRILLION creates value for

- *citizens*, being part of the design of the solution they will significantly increase their customer satisfaction on the services provided by LEAs;
- *LEAs*, as a consequence of the citizens' involvement in the definition of TRILLION, will be sure they adopt a platform which is significantly helping people, overcoming issues that are not necessarily technological, such as resistance to adoption, resistance to change, and limited trust citizens may have towards the Internet, etc.

The crucial role of the end users

The active involvement of the end-users, citizens and LEAs, is crucial in TRILLION: the end-users are the ones who can provide input from the operational perspective as well as the main beneficiaries of the services implemented in the context of the project.

The project's objective is to allow citizens and LEAs to interactively talk to each other creating a new *participatory environment* and supporting new forms of interaction, citizens engagement and citizen sourcing.

The TRILLION project has started building a strong community of end-users guiding the project as it develops and helping to ensure that the final product has genuine value and practical application to both LEAs and citizens.

Join us today!
Don't miss this
opportunity to tell us
what you think about
TRILLION!

Thanks to your support
we will deliver
a user friendly APP,
tested
across **5** locations
(Ancona, Eindhoven, Lecce, Lisbon,
North East England)

Join us at

<http://trillion-project.eng.it>
(check out the "Join us" section on the website)

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